

Textile-based Green Energy Assisted UHF RFID Tag with Enhanced Read Range

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Abstract—Passive ultra-high-frequency (UHF) radio-frequency identification (RFID) technology is considered an excellent last-mile solution. However, its read range is limited due to reliance on RF backscattering. To address this issue, this paper presents a UHF RFID tag that harvests external energy from two additional sources, solar and thermal, to extend the tag’s communication range. The proposed tag design consists of dipole-like structure fabricated using conductive textile material and commercially available EM4325 tag IC. Moreover, a custom-built thermal energy harvesting (TEG) circuit, and four different commercially available solar cells have been utilized for performance evaluation of the proposed tag in terms of read range. A thin-film Panasonic amorphous solar cell AM-5907CAR and flexible PV cells are used to harvest solar energy. The performance of the designed UHF RFID tag was evaluated in an outdoor environment using a fixed-position JADAK ThingMagic M6e RFID reader. The measured results indicate that the use of additional energy sources increases the read range by 2 times with solar energy and by 1.8 times with the TEG, when compared to the read range of the baseline tag. Therefore, the utilization of flexible conductive textile material and integration of different energy harvesting options make this tag design a promising option for wearable IoT applications.

Keywords—Energy harvesting, RF, solar, thermal, textile antenna, RFID, battery-less Internet of Things

I. INTRODUCTION

Internet of Things (IoT) and ultra-high-frequency (UHF) radio-frequency identification (RFID) are paired to create innovative industrial and commercial applications ranging from consumer devices/sensors to infotainment solutions. The global economic value of IoT is expected between \$5.5 to \$12.6 trillion by 2030 [1]. UHF RFID technology is an integral part of the IoT ecosystem due to its low cost, inkjet-printable tag antenna, and multi-tag read capabilities. Moreover, UHF RFID technology can further help expand IoT applications by providing low power sensing solutions, paving the way to identify and track objects, sensing environmental parameters, enabling better connectivity and data collection. Moreover, RFID technology can be used in different fields such as agriculture [2], inventory systems [3], healthcare [4] and many others.

Passive UHF tags are more attractive candidates due to their battery-free operation and energy backscattering mechanism with the reader device. However, passive tags fail to achieve long read range and strong communication capability because of their battery-less nature [6]. On the other hand, semi-passive tags harvest energy from RF signals and are also capable of harvesting energy from other sources. Active tags have their own transmitter and power source, enabling them to communicate with the receiver over a longer distance. Semi-passive and active tags are good options in providing longer

read ranges compared to passive tags. However, the downside of active tags is that they have design constraints such as cost, size, scheduled replacement cycles [5]. The semi-passive RFID tags have the ability to overcome the limited read range by using additional energy sources. In [6], the authors state that adding a battery or harvester extends communication ranges and enables more power-demanding sensors.

This motivated us to design and implement a hybrid energy harvesting (EH) RFID tag to extend its communication range. Energy can be harvested through different sources such as thermal, solar, and RF energy, each offering distinct advantages depending on the application environment and available ambient energy. Among these, RF energy is an inherent energy source for RFID tags, as it is continuously provided by the reader device. Solar energy represents one of the most promising options due to its high energy density and easy integration with UHF RFID tags, especially for outdoor environments. Thermal energy sources can also be utilized due to the constant availability of heat sources in industrial environments and for wearable applications, enabling continuous energy generation from temperature gradients. The corresponding energy harvesters can be implemented as plug and play components and provide improved communication range, when required.

In the literature, there has been works on solar-based EH systems that use photovoltaic (PV) cells [7], [8] and flexible PV cells [9] to extend read-range. On the other hand, there are also research on extending the tag’s range using thermal EH systems [10]. In [11], a unique hybrid EH was presented, along with the corresponding antenna design. However, most of the aforementioned research studies lack an analysis of different energy-harvesting elements on the read-range performance of passive RFID tags, such as thermal energy harvesting and solar panels with different dimensions. Moreover, most of previous RFID EH studies focus on harvested power or achievable read range only, leaving read time results under different EH scenarios unexplored.

Therefore, we propose a solution for read range enhancement of passive UHF RFID tags by experimentally validating the read range performance of a passive RFID tag using two different external energy sources, namely thermal energy and solar PV. To this end, this research incorporates a conductive textile-based antenna to explore different energy-harvesting options and provides an analysis of the UHF RFID tag performance in terms of read range and received signal strength indicator (RSSI) measurements. Moreover, the utilization of a flexible textile-based antenna makes the proposed tag more suitable for wearable IoT applications. A UHF RFID tag antenna is simulated and fabricated using textile material and

integrated with a commercially available EM4325 UHF RFID IC [12]. The thermal energy-harvesting source is developed and integrated with the RFID system to assess its feasibility for low-power sensing applications. Additionally, four different commercially available solar cells are used. The performance of the designed tag is evaluated in terms of read range in an outdoor environment using a JADAK ThingMagic M6e RFID reader.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the concept and design of the proposed hybrid powered tag. Section III describes the experimental setup and performance evaluation in realistic conditions. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper and discusses potential directions for future research.

II. CONCEPT AND DESIGN OF HYBRID POWERED RFID TAG

This section presents key components of the proposed UHF RFID tag. The proposed tag uses a commercially available EM4325 RFID IC that operates within the 860–960 MHz frequency band and complies with EPCglobal Class-1 Generation-2 as defined by ISO/IEC 18000-63 and ISO/IEC 18000-64. The EM4325 supports two modes of operation and can function either as a passive or semi-passive tag, depending on the availability of a power source. It requires a minimum operating voltage of 1.25 V, while the maximum allowable voltage is 3.65 V. The pin configuration of the EM4325 IC is shown in Fig. 1. The EM4325 IC consists of eight pins, of which only three are utilized in this work: ANT+, VSS, and VBAT. The ANT+ and VSS pins are used for connecting the antenna, enabling RF communication with the reader. The VBAT and VSS pins serve as the external power interface, which in this work is supplied by the energy harvester (EH). This configuration allows the tag to operate in both passive and semi-passive modes, depending on the availability of harvested energy.

Fig. 1. Pin description of EM4325 IC [12]

This tag consists of a dipole like structure as shown in Fig. 2 (a). The performance of the proposed tag design in terms of impedance matching is simulated in CST Microwave studio [13]. To demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed hybrid RFID tag, a conductive textile-based antenna is designed on a PET substrate. The antenna material [14] has a thickness of 0.1 mm and a sheet resistance of 4 mΩ/sq, measured using the four-probe method. This corresponds to a conductivity of 2.5×10^6 S/m, indicating good electrical performance suitable for RFID antenna fabrication. The substrate has a thickness of 80 μm and a relative permittivity (ϵ_r) of 3.2. The antenna model is created and simulated in CST Microwave Studio. To measure the

Fig. 2. (a) Simulated model of proposed tag antenna (b) Fabricated prototype of proposed tag design

input impedance of the EM4325 IC integrated with the breakout SOP08 adapter, a HIOKI IM7585 impedance analyzer is used. The simulated design shows an S11 value of -26.42 dB at 866 MHz, demonstrating good impedance matching between the EM4325 IC and the antenna, as well as an omnidirectional radiation pattern. The antenna is then fabricated and connected to the EM4325 IC using conductive silver epoxy provided by CircuitWorks for performance evaluation. A prototype of the proposed tag design is fabricated for experimentation and performance validation, as shown in Fig. 2(b).

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

A. Integration of different EH options with proposed RFID tag

The thermal EH circuit is based on the LTC3108 ultra-low-voltage step-up converter [15], which is specifically designed to operate from very low input voltages, such as those generated by a TEG, as shown in Fig. 3. The designed thermal EH source converts small temperature differences into electrical energy, typically in the range of 20 mV to 500 mV. This voltage is insufficient to power most electronic devices, so a 1:100 step-up transformer is used to boost the input voltage to a level suitable for the LTC3108 converter. The converter stores the harvested energy in external capacitors and provides a voltage of 3.3 V to power the RFID tag IC, enabling semi-passive operation and improving the tag's communication range.

The circuit of the solar-based EH system is shown in Fig. 4 and consists of a PV cell, a PN diode, a Zener diode, and a supercapacitor. The Zener diode is used for voltage regulation and protection. The PN diode prevents reverse current flow

Fig. 3. Thermal-based EH circuit

Fig. 4. Solar-based EH circuit

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Read range measurement setup consists of (a) JADAK ThingMagic M6e RFID reader and antenna, (b) ThingMagic Universal Reader Assistant software

from the supercapacitor to the PV cell. The supercapacitor acts as an energy storage element, providing a stable output voltage to the RFID tag. The antenna is the key component of the tag and is responsible for receiving the signal from the reader and facilitating data exchange.

B. Performance analysis of proposed RFID tag

This subsection presents the experimental setup used to evaluate the performance of the developed hybrid-powered RFID tag using different EH sources in outdoor conditions. The setup consists of a fixed-position JADAK ThingMagic M6e RFID reader operating at a frequency of 868 MHz with vertical linear polarization and a receiver antenna, as shown in Fig. 5 (a). The designed RFID tag mounted on a movable chair. The reader is connected to a laptop running the ThingMagic Universal Reader Assistant software, which is used to configure reader parameters, monitor tag responses, and record read performance data, as shown in Fig. 5(b). Markers are placed on the ground at one-meter intervals to maintain consistent spacing between the reader and the tag during measurements. All experiments are conducted in line-of-sight outdoor conditions.

The first series of measurements was performed using the UHF RFID tag in its passive configuration to measure its baseline read range. The theoretical read range of the RFID tag can be estimated using the Friis transmission equation [9], adapted for backscatter systems:

$$d = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} \sqrt{\frac{P_{TX} G_{tag} G_{reader} \tau}{P_{IC}}} \quad (1)$$

where P_{TX} is the transmitted power, G_{tag} and G_{reader} are the antenna gains of the tag and reader, respectively, τ is the power transmission coefficient, and P_{IC} is the minimum activation power of the RFID IC. When the tag is powered by an external source (battery or energy harvester), the available voltage at the IC is no longer limited by P_{IC} . In this case, the maximum range depends mainly on the strength of the backscattered signal detected by the reader. Therefore, supplying external energy to the tag effectively reduces its dependence on the reader field, enabling longer read ranges and shorter read times, as observed experimentally.

Fig. 6 shows the read range achieved with RF, thermal, and battery sources. It can be seen that the passive tag achieved a maximum read range of approximately 4 m when relying only on the energy transmitted by the reader. In the second scenario, a 3 V coin-cell battery was connected to the VBAT and VSS pins of the EM4325 IC. The third measurement utilized the thermal EH circuit described in Fig. 3, in which a TEG supplied energy through the LTC3108 boost converter. The TEG module used in this experiment was the SP1848-27145, which generates voltage when a temperature difference is established between its two sides. This was achieved by placing the cold side of the TEG against a metal heatsink

Fig. 6. Ranges achieved with RF, Thermal and Battery

cooled to approximately 12 °C, while the top side was warmed by contact with a human hand, creating the necessary thermal gradient to power the converter. In practice, the temperature gradient can be achieved by placing the TEG in contact with any part of the human body, enabling continuous power generation from body heat. The battery-powered configuration provided a good read enhancement of approximately 9 m as compared to 4 m in passive tag scenario. The thermal EH setup followed closely by achieving a range of around 8 m which demonstrated the effectiveness of the TEG-based power supply.

In the next series of measurements, we evaluated different solar-based EH configurations. In these measurements, each solar cell was first connected directly to the EM4325 IC, with the positive side of the solar cell connected to the VSS pin and the negative side to the VBAT pin. The tested solar cells included a non-flexible Panasonic amorphous solar cell (AM-5907CAR) and three different thin-film PowerFilm amorphous silicon flexible PV cells: SP3-37, ONP2.4-15×94, and MP3-25 [16]. The characteristics of each solar panel are shown in Table I. In the supercapacitor-based EH configuration, a 5 F, 2.7 V supercapacitor was used; however, other capacitance values (e.g., 10 F) can also be implemented, with charging time scaling proportionally with capacitance. Using each panel’s operating current, the ideal charging time for a 5 F capacitor from 0 V to 2.7 V is shown in Table II.

TABLE I. SOLAR PANEL CHARACTERISTICS

Solar panel	Dimension (cm)	Operating Voltage (V)	Operating Current (mA)
AM-5907CAR	5.5 x 7.5	5.9	45.7
ONP2.4-15x94	9.4 x 1.46	2.4	18.6
SP3-37	6.4 x 3.65	3	22
MP3-25	11.4 x 2.4	3	31

TABLE II. 5-F SUPERCAPACITOR CHARGE TIME

Solar Panel	Calculated Charge Time (min)	Estimated Real Charge Time (min)
AM-5907CAR	4.9	6–7
ONP2.4-15x94	12.1	14–17
SP3-37	10.2	12–14
MP3-25	7.3	9–10

Fig. 7. Ranges achieved with different Solar panels and Supercapacitor circuit

Fig. 7 shows that among the solar-powered configurations, the AM-5907CAR panel achieved a comparable range of 8 m, while the SP3-37 flexible panel performed slightly below that value. The ONP2.4-15×94 panel delivered the shortest range at around 6 m, whereas the MP3-25 panel achieved the best solar-based performance, slightly exceeding 8 m.

Moreover, the enhancement in read range performance observed for each solar-based configuration correlates with the electrical characteristics of the respective solar panels. It is found that integrating PV panels with higher operating voltage and current output (as shown in Table I) results in longer reading ranges when used with the proposed RFID tags. However, since the EM4325 IC operates up to a maximum voltage of 3.65 V, supplying voltages above this threshold does not further enhance performance. The excess energy is internally limited and does not contribute to additional range. In all solar-based measurements, the recorded RSSI values showed fluctuations across distance, primarily due to variations in sunlight received by the solar cells during testing. To address this, a final measurement was conducted using the MP3-25 connected to the complete supercapacitor-based EH circuit, as described in Section II and shown in Fig. 4. This configuration achieved a similar maximum range of slightly above 8 m, but the RSSI plot shows a smooth, steady decline with distance and no fluctuations, as shown in Fig. 7. This behavior confirms that the supercapacitor-based circuit provides a stable voltage and current output to the IC, ensuring consistent tag performance regardless of varying sunlight conditions.

Fig. 8. Read times achieved with different energy sources

Fig. 8 presents the total time taken by the RFID reader to complete 50 successful tag readings when the tag is connected to different energy sources. Shorter read times indicate stable and sufficient power delivery, while longer read times reflect weaker or unstable energy supply and communication. The results show that the available supply voltage and current have a direct impact on read time. The RF-only configuration exhibited the longest duration of around 8 s, since the tag relied entirely on the reader. Supplementing the tag with external energy sources reduced the read time proportionally to the stability of the supplied energy. The solar-powered tag showed partial improvement (7.43 s), though illumination fluctuations caused inconsistent powering and delayed responses. When a supercapacitor-based EH circuit was added, the supply stabilized, reducing the read time to 4.3 s. This matches the performance of the battery-powered configuration. The thermal-powered configuration provided the most stable and continuous energy delivery, resulting in the shortest read time of 3.93 s.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents a multi-source EH-powered tag that leverages external energy sources to enhance the read range. The design demonstrates the integration of a custom-built TEG and several commercially available solar cells with a textile- was evaluated in terms of communication range and read times under various conditions. The results indicate that the based UHF RFID tag. The performance of the proposed tag achieved a maximum read range of approximately 4 m when powered solely by the JADAK ThingMagic M6e RFID reader. The communication range was further extended to about 9 m when the tag was connected to a 3 V coin-cell battery. Using the TEG device, the communication range increased by approximately two times compared to the conventional RF-powered method. Among the different solar cells tested, the tag achieved the best performance of up to 8 m when connected to the MP3-25 solar cell. In terms of read time, the thermal and solar + capacitor configurations provided the most stable and continuous power delivery, resulting in the shortest read times of 3.93 s and 4.3 s, respectively. These results highlight the potential of using different energy sources with RFID tags to achieve improved communication range and read times, particularly in environments with ambient energy availability. Future work will focus on the design and development of a green, organic, and printed hybrid-powered UHF RFID tag for continuous environmental monitoring applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. C. Michael Chui, and Mark Patel "The Internet of Things: Catching up to an accelerating opportunity", McKinsey & Company, Nov. 2021.
- [2] S. Gómez-Gijón *et al.*, "Printed RFID sensing system: The cost-effective way to IoT smart agriculture," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 232, pp. 110116, 2025.
- [3] H. Li, S. Alfayoumi, M. Gatnau-Sarret, R. Bhattacharyya, J. Melià-Seguí, and S. Sarma, "ResNet-Enhanced DFSA: A Time-Efficient UHF RFID Inventory System for Large-Scale Applications" in *2025 IEEE International Conference on AI and Data Analytics*, Medford, USA, 2025, pp. 1-8.
- [4] C. Luo, I. Gil, and R. Fernández-García, "Electro-Textile UHF-RFID Compression Sensor for Health-Caring Applications," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 22, no. 12, pp. 12332-12338, 2022.

- [5] F. Costa, S. Genovesi, M. Borgese, A. Michel, F. A. Dicandia, and G. Manara, "A Review of RFID Sensors, the New Frontier of Internet of Things," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 9, pp. 3138, doi: 10.3390/s21093138, 2021
- [6] H. Solar, A. Beriain, R. Berenguer, J. Sosa, and J. Montiel-Nelson, "Semi-Passive UHF RFID Sensor tags: A comprehensive review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 135583-135599, 2023.
- [7] S. N. R. Kantareddy, I. Mathews, R. Bhattacharyya, I. M. Peters, T. Buonassisi, and S. E. Sarma, "Long Range Battery-Less PV-Powered RFID Tag Sensors," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 6989-6996, 2019.
- [8] A. Fereshtian, R. Gonzalez, J. Berenguer Sau, F. Reverter, and M. Gasulla, *Read-Range Extension with Semi-Passive Tags Powered by PV Cells. UbiComp/ISWC, Espoo, Finland 2025*, 10.1145/3714394.3756150
- [9] S. N. R. Kantareddy, R. Bhattacharya, S. E. Sarma, I. Mathews, J. Thapa, L. Zhe, S. Sun, I. M. Peters, and T. Buonassisi, "Introducing flexible perovskites to the IoT world using photovoltaic-powered wireless tags," 2022, arXiv:2207.00227
- [10] H. Solar, A. Beriain, A. Rezola, D. d. Rio, and R. Berenguer, "A 22-m Operation Range Semi-Passive UHF RFID Sensor Tag With Flexible Thermoelectric Energy Harvester," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 22, no. 20, pp. 19797-19808, 2022.
- [11] S. G. Veloo, J. J. Tiang, S. Muhammad, and S. K. Wong, "A Hybrid Solar-RF Energy Harvesting System Based on an EM4325-Embedded RFID Tag," *Electronics*, vol. 12, no. 19, pp. 4045, 2023.
- [12] EM MICROELECTRONIC, RFID IC EM4325, Available https://www.emmicroelectronic.com/sites/default/files/products/datasheet/s/4325-ds_0.pdf, [15 November 2025].
- [13] D. Syst'emes, CST Microwave Studios <https://www.3ds.com/products/simulia/cst-studio-suite>
- [14] Shieldex® Nora Dell CR <https://www.shieldex.de/en/products/shieldex-nora-dell-cr/> Last accessed date: [15 November 2025].
- [15] Ultralow Voltage Step-Up Converter and Power Manager, <https://www.analog.com/media/en/technical-documentation/datasheets/31081fb.pdf>. Last accessed date: [15 November 2025]
- [16] PowerFilm Solar Panels, https://eu.mouser.com/datasheet/2/1009/Electronic_Component_Spec_Sheet_Cla_77DEA84523C82-1658524.pdf, Last accessed date: [15 November 2025].